
Role of Panchakarma in Chronic Diseases for Public Health

Dr. Rampal¹, Dr. Sanjana Mogre¹, Dr. Rajeev Kumar Pandey²

¹PG Scholar, Dept. of Panchakarma, MMM Govt. Ayurveda College, Udaipur, Rajasthan India

²Associate Professor, Dept. of Panchakarma, MMM Govt. Ayurveda College, Udaipur, Rajasthan India.

Abstract Chronic diseases constitute a major global public health challenge, accounting for the majority of morbidity, mortality, and healthcare expenditure worldwide. Non-communicable diseases such as diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular disorders, arthritis, respiratory illnesses, neurological conditions, and psychosomatic disorders are often lifelong, progressive, and require long-term management. Conventional medicine primarily focuses on symptom control and disease containment, whereas traditional systems like Ayurveda emphasize holistic health promotion, disease prevention, and root-cause management. Panchakarma, a unique detoxification and bio-purification therapy of Ayurveda, plays a significant role in the prevention and management of chronic diseases. This article reviews the principles, mechanisms, therapeutic applications, and public health relevance of Panchakarma, highlighting its potential as a complementary strategy in chronic disease management and health promotion.

Keywords: Panchakarma, Chronic disease, Ayurveda, Public health, Preventive medicine.

Introduction

Ayurveda is Science of life. The main Aim of Ayurveda is Swasthasya Swasthya Rakshanam and Aturasya Vikara prashamanam ch(1). In today's stressed-out and dangerous environment, our bodily and mental systems accumulate pollutants, leading to a variety of diseases that can be harmful to an Individual's health and well-being. Panchakarma is a traditional Ayurvedic practice designed to cleanse and rejuvenate the body. As modern medicine often struggles to prevent chronic and serious health issues, many people are returning to this ancient detoxification method. It has been applied successfully in managing autoimmune, neurological, psychiatric, musculoskeletal, and metabolic disorders. Panchakarma aims to enhance the bioavailability of drugs, restore physiological balance, eliminate disease-causing toxins, and halt the progression or recurrence of illnesses. Today, healthcare professionals in India and across the world employ these therapies both for prevention and treatment. The core techniques include Vamana (therapeutic vomiting), Virechana (therapeutic purgation), Basti—such as Asthapan Basti (decoction enema) and Anuvasana Basti (oil enema)—Nasya Karma (nasal administration of medicines), and Raktamokshana (bloodletting). Prior to Panchakarma procedures, Snehana (therapeutic oleation) and Svedana (sudation) therapies are carried out to prepare the body's system for the removal of bio-toxins and for cleansing of strotas Samshodhana (purification), Samshamana (pacification) and Nidana Parivarjana (elimination of causative factors) among them. While Samshamana therapy can sometimes allow disorders to resurface due to underlying causes or unfavourable environmental influences, Panchakarma therapy is considered more effective. By thoroughly cleansing the body and expelling toxins, Panchakarma not only provides rapid

relief but also minimizes the likelihood of recurrence (2). making it especially valuable in maintaining long-term health.

Methodology

Material

Ayurvedic samhita and their Commentaries
Journal and Internet

Method

Collection and Compilation of Literature related to panchakarma procedure and its role in maintenance of Health and Management of chronic diseases.

This is Literary Study under title Role of Panchakarma in Chronic Diseases for Public Health.

Review of Literature

Concept of Chronic Disease in Ayurveda

Ayurveda views health as a state of equilibrium among Dosha (Vata, Pitta, Kapha), Dhātu, Mala, and Agni, along with mental and spiritual harmony. Chronic diseases are often described as “Chirakari Vyadhi”, resulting from long-standing doshic imbalance, accumulation of metabolic toxins (Ama), impaired digestion (Mandagni), and obstruction of body channels (Srotorodha).

Unlike acute diseases, chronic conditions are deeply rooted and require systematic purification (Shodhana) followed by rejuvenation (Rasayana). Panchakarma is the principal Shodhana therapy designed to eliminate Vitiated Doshas and restore physiological balance.

Panchakarma procedure – An Overview

Panchakarma literally means “five actions” and consists of five major therapeutic procedures aimed at detoxification and purification:

Vamana (Therapeutic emesis)

Virechana (Therapeutic purgation)

Basti (Medicated enema – Asthapana and Anuvasana)

Nasya (Nasal administration of medicines)

Raktamokshana (Bloodletting)

These procedures are preceded into three steps

1. Purva karma (Deepana, Pachana, Snehana, Swedan)
2. Pradhan karma (Vaman, virechan, Basti, Nasya, Raktamokshana)
3. Paschat karma (peyadi or Tarpanadi Sansarjan krama)

Deepana and Pachana

These procedures are used to clean the Strotas's and Ama (toxins), which makes it simple for the toxins to be separated and eliminated during the initial detoxification process. The body must be prepared before beginning any major purifying process. so that the body can be properly detoxified and the best outcomes can be obtained. Deepana and Pachana are helpful in this condition. Internally Medicines are administered for this reason. This Depending on the patient and Bala of vyadhi (3).

Snehana and Swedana

Snehana- After Deepana and Pachana, the entire body is oiled using Snehapana (oral) and Abhyanga (massage). Patients are told to ingest a specific quantity of therapeutic ghee or oil for a predetermined duration of time according to their Koshtha and Agni. The dosage of medicinal ghee or oil is gradually increased each day. The completion of Snehapana could take 3 to 7 days. Snehapana therapy involves both Snehapana and Abhyanga, which soften the body and dissolve the Vitiated Doshas in order to treat the Vitiated Vata Dosha (4).

Swedana - Swedana is the practices of inducing perspiration with the help of steam and medicinal herbal decoction. Ayurvedic fomentation is usually given following an oil massage (5).

Pradhan karma**Vamana**

Vamana karma is mainly used to remove Vitiated Kapha Dosha. In addition to Kapha Dosha, it is also used to remove Kapha Pitta Dosha. Vamana karma can be done by using various drugs but Madanphala is most popular Drugs Having properties like Ushna(hot), Tikshna (sharp), Sukshma (subtle), Vyavayi (those that circulate the entire body before being digested) and Vikasi (those that cause joint looseness) reach the heart and circulate via the vessels due to their potency. They liquify and separate the adhered Doshas because of predominance of Agni Mahabhuta. The Vitiated Dosha reached the stomach and expelled with the help of Udan Vayu (6).

Virechana

Virechana karma, is the process of removing Vitiated Doshas (toxins or waste) through the rectum. Virechana karma purifies the blood, rids the body of excess Pitta-Kapha, and removes impurities from the body. The therapy completely detoxifies the gastro-intestinal tract by concentrating on toxins accumulated in the liver and gall bladder (7).

Basti

Niruha Basti - The specialized Panchakarma procedure Basti is Used to treat Vata diseases. It is mostly used in the treatment for Vitiated Vata Dosha. In this method herbal decoction according to dosha is used to achieve Dosha equilibrium (8).

Anuvasana Basti- Anuvasana Basti is used to cure severe dryness with a good digestive fire and are purely Vatavyadhi (nervous System, musculoskeletal disorder) In This method Oil can be utilized to achieve Vata Dosha Equilibrium (9).

Nasya - The nose is considered as the main pathway to the head, thus giving medicine (10) Through this route it is very Useful to cure Urdhva Jatrugat Vikara means Diseases of the parts above the Shoulders. Nasya must be given to the patient on an empty stomach, with the patient Lying down with their head tilted back and The Nasya drug administered in each Nostril (11).

Raktmokshan

The four components of life—the soul (Atma), mind (Mana), senses (Indriya), and body—are thought to be affected by the condition of the blood, which is said to be the carrier of Ayu. For prevention of blood-borne disorders, it is necessary to remove toxic blood from the body. Raktamokshana is used to remove impure blood from body and treat conditions like Swelling, skin diseases, tumour, debility, Sinusitis, suppuration and bleeding Disorders etc.

Paschat karma- Changes in Diet and lifestyle after Panchakarma.

Example - Peyadi or Tarpanadi Samsarjana Krama (12).

Panchakarma in Disease Prevention and Health Promotion

From a public health standpoint, Panchakarma is not limited to disease treatment but also plays a preventive role. Seasonal Panchakarma (Ritushodhana) helps in maintaining Doshic balance, preventing disease onset, and enhancing immunity.

Table 1: Different Ritu (Seasons) and Panchakarma procedures

Season	Panchakarma procedure
Varsha (<i>Vata Prakopa</i>)	<i>Basti</i>
Vasant (<i>kapha prakopa</i>)	<i>Vaman</i>
Sharad (<i>Pitta Prakopa</i>)	<i>Virechana</i>
Pravruta, Sharad, Vasant	<i>Nasya</i>
Sharad (<i>Rakta Dushti</i>)	<i>Raktmokshan</i>

Role of Panchakarma in Specific Chronic Diseases**i. Metabolic Disorders**

Conditions such as obesity, diabetes mellitus, dyslipidaemia, and metabolic syndrome are major public health concerns. Panchakarma therapies like Virechana and Lekhana Basti help in reducing excess Kapha and Meda, improving insulin sensitivity, and correcting lipid metabolism.

ii. Musculoskeletal Disorders

Chronic conditions such as osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, cervical and lumbar spondylosis cause long-term disability. Basti therapy is considered the best treatment for Vata disorders and helps reduce pain, stiffness, and functional limitations.

iii. Cardiovascular Diseases

Hypertension, ischemic heart disease, and atherosclerosis are linked to stress, inflammation, and metabolic imbalance. Panchakarma, along with lifestyle modification, supports cardiovascular health by improving circulation, reducing stress, and balancing Doshas.

iv. Respiratory Diseases

Bronchial asthma, chronic bronchitis, and allergic rhinitis often show recurrent episodes. Vamana and Nasya therapies help in expelling excess Kapha, clearing airways, and reducing recurrence.

v. Neurological and Psychosomatic Disorders

Conditions such as migraine, anxiety, depression, insomnia, and stress-related disorders benefit from Panchakarma through nervous system stabilization and mental rejuvenation.

vi. Skin and Autoimmune Disorders

Chronic skin diseases and autoimmune conditions involve immune dysregulation. Raktamokshana and Virechana are traditionally indicated for blood-borne and inflammatory disorders.

Table 2: Diseases treated according to Panchakarma procedures

Disease	Panchakarma
<i>Sthaulya</i> (Obesity)	<i>Udvardana, (Ruksha) Pinda swedana and Lekhanbasti</i>
<i>Prameha</i> (Diabetes)	<i>Vamana, Virechana, Udvardana</i>
<i>Kushtha</i> (Skin disorder)	<i>Vamana, Virechana, Raktamokshana and Nasya</i>
<i>Sandhigataavata</i> (Osteoarthritis)	<i>Snehana, Swedana and Basti</i>
<i>Amavata</i> (Rheumatoid Arthritis)	<i>Pachana, Virechana, Anuvasana basti, Kshar Basti and Valuka Swedana</i>
<i>Pakshavadha</i> (paralysis)	<i>Mridu Virechana, Asthapana basti, Anuvasan basti, Snehana and Swedana</i>
<i>Amlapitta</i> (Gastritis)	<i>Vamana and Virechana</i>
<i>Shwas</i> (COPD)	<i>Vamana, Virechana and Swedana</i>
<i>Shiroroga</i> (Headache)	<i>Nasya and Virechana</i>
<i>Anidra</i> (insomnia)	<i>Shirodhara, Nasya, Abhyanga, Utsadana</i>
<i>Udara roga</i> (Ascites)	<i>Nitya Virechan</i>

To cure disease- Is the second aim of Ayurveda, all diseases are treated with panchakarma because disease are the results Vitiated Doshas.

Discussion

Due to Globalisation, Deforestation, pollution, Stress, change in diet and lifestyle, our body remains malnourished. Due to These several factors occurs various health Challenges. Cases of disease such as cardiovascular disease, respiratory disorders, obesity, Diabetes, renal disease, Anxiety, Depression are increasing day by day. Therefore, our Health is always a concern. Hetusevan causes imbalance in metabolic system which leads Agnimandya and production of Ama which get accumulated in various channels, responsible for Vitiating of Dosha and manifestation of various disease.

Panchakarma procedure especially used restore the integrity of strotas, helps to keep the body's Dosha's in balance, eliminate toxins via nearest possible route of elimination, and stop the progression of existing illnesses. It serves the main purpose of Ayurveda that is maintenance of health and management of disease. Panchakarma helps in maintenance of health. By enhancing Jatharagni (digestive fire and metabolism), treating illnesses, maintaining the balance of the Doshas, and improving colour, complexity, mind, and intelligence, Additionally, it boosts a person's power and vitality, enabling them to live longer and in better health.

Purvakarma like Snehana and swedana helps to ripen and liquify the Dosha, Dosha get detached causes Doshotklesha, because of this Dosha move towards Koshta which makes easy to eliminate toxins.

Vamana removes Vitiated Kapha, lightens the body, increases the activities of sense organs, and clears the channels of the chest, flanks, and head area when done correctly.

Virechana purifies vitiated Pitta from grahani, Duodenum, biliary system and clears all body channels, generating Jatharagni and Imparting lightness to the body when performed correctly.

Basti helps to remove Vitiated Vata from Pakvashaya by ensuring correct faeces, urine, and flatus ejection, as well as enhancing appetite and Taste, and creates happiness. The aggravated Dosha above Urdhva Jatru Pradesh is removed by Nasya Karma, which also clears the circulation pathways (head and neck).

Raktamokshana helps to remove impure blood and prevents various raktapradoshaja Vyadhi.

Conclusion

Ayurveda's unique gift to human well-being, panchakarma, is unmatched. When used properly, these treatments have the potential to provide amazing results. For Successful result of Panchakarma. Purva Karma, Pradhana Karma, and Paschat Karma must all be done without any fault. When used correctly, Panchakarma therapy eliminates Doshas, treats ailments, and restores one's natural Strength and complexion, all of which contribute to a longer and better life. Elimination therapies, on the other hand, entirely eliminate Vitiated Doshas from their source, ensuring that they don't reappear unless there are very strong etiological causes. It has benefited various public health problem Globally as well. Panchakarma therapy improves strength, longevity, and the eradication of ailments, and is advantageous to both those with illness and those in good health.

References

- [1]. Agnivesha, charak samhita Sutrasthan Arthedashamahamuliya adhyaya, verse 26 edited by Acharya Shukla V. and Tripathi R.D. reprint Delhi, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishthan :2004; 447
- [2]. Agnivesha, charak samhita Sutrasthan Chikitsa prabhritiya adhyaya, verse 21 edited by Acharya Shukla V. and Tripathi R.D. reprint Delhi, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishthan :2004; 252
- [3]. Sharangdhara, Sharangdhara Samhita with Adhamalla's Dipika and Kashirama's Gudarth dipika commentary Prathama khanda Deepana pachana adhyaya verse 1 edited by pandit Shastri P ; Bombay ; Pandurang Jawaji publication ;1931, 34-35 4. 5. 6. 7. 8. 9. 10.
- [4]. Agnivesha, charak samhita Sutrasthan Snehadhyaya, verse 29 edited by Acharya Shukla V. and Tripathi R.D. reprint Delhi, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishthan : 2004; 202
- [5]. Agnivesha, charak samhita Sutrasthan Swedadhyaya, verse 4,5 edited by Acharya Shukla V. and Tripathi R.D. reprint Delhi, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishthan : 2004; 217
- [6]. Agnivesha Charaka Samhita Kalpasthana, Madanaphalakalpa – 1/5 edited by Acharya Shukla V. and Tripathi R.D. reprint Delhi, Varanasi, India: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishthan;2014, 790
- [7]. Agnivesha, charak samhita Sutrasthan Snehadhyaya, verse 29 edited by Acharya Shukla V. and Tripathi R.D. reprint Delhi, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishthan : 2004; 202
- [8]. Agnivesha Charaka. Siddhithana, Panchakarmiyamsiddhi – 2/verse 16. Edited by Acharya Shukla V. and Tripathi R.D. Varanasi, India: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan;2014, 876
- [9]. Agnivesha Charaka. Siddhithana, Panchakarmiyamsiddhi – 2/verse 17. Edited by Acharya Shukla V. and Tripathi R.D. Delhi, India: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishthan;2014, 877
- [10]. Vagbhat, Ashtang Hruday, Sutra Sthana, Nasyavidhimadhyaya 20/1, Edited by Tripathi B., Delhi, Chaukhambha sanskrut pratishthan; 2022, 244
- [11]. Vagbhat, Ashtang Hruday, Sutra Sthana, Nasyavidhimadhyaya 20/17-20, Edited by Tripathi B., Delhi, Chaukhambha sanskrut pratishthan; 2022, 247
- [12]. Agnivesha Charaka. Siddhithana, Kalpanasiddhirdhyaya – 1/ 11 Edited by Acharya Shukla V. and Tripathi R.D. Varanasi, India: Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan;2013, 861

